

Learning Innovation of Educational Equality in Indonesia

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Abstract

This qualitative research aimed to describe learning innovation of educational equality in homeschooling Indonesia. Research strategy used is cased study by choosing the research site at Homeschooling in Surakarta. The theory used in this research is Bourdieu's theory of social practices. Qualitative research with a research strategy of case study to support and determine alternative models of education. Sampling used purposive sampling with informants consisted of the director, teachers, staff, homeschool students, and parents. Data collection is done through in-depth interviews, participant observation, and documentation. The results showed that Homeschooling in Surakarta applied study at home method. The process of mentoring students used two approaches to get to know and understand the progress of their students. First was psychological approach. Second is the academic approach, the given learning system put forward learning modal by adjusting the level of ability, learning style, and communication character of students. These methods and approaches were used in learning for the development of equality education in homeschooling.

Keywords: Homeschooling, Education, Educational Model, Innovation, Child.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the most essential things, especially for children. It is the process by which a person establishes abilities, attitudes, and other forms of constructive behavior in the society they live (Good, 1959). Initially, the community teaches and instills values, knowledge, and skills to children through families with primary socialization that takes place since childhood. Thus, in the future, they can play a life role appropriately (Triyanto, 2014). Educational activities performed by parents or communities that are not organized are commonly called informal education. It is connected to informal settings such as friends, family and work (Dib, 1988). However, as the increasingly complex society keeps developing, various educational institutions have emerged. Indonesia admits three educational pathways as described in Article 13 of Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, including formal education, non-formal education, and informal education. Formal education is hierarchical, provided by qualified teachers in institutional settings, guided by the curriculum, approved by the government, and funded from the national funds (Latchem, 2018). Generally, this form of education consists of instructors, students and institutions. Formal education is the primary focus of the Human Resources (HR) development and is given great attention from the community and the government. The participants of formal education are expected to attend classes, adhere to the rules of learning and assessment aimed to access the next stage, and produce diploma and degree achievements (Todaro, 1995). On one side, many problems are still faced. First, access to education remains difficult. Many children drop out of school or cannot obtain a proper education. The second problem deals with quality. Even children who study in formal schools may not be able to obtain the learning quality as expected. Finally, inequality problem covers various aspects that require physical integration so that education can be distributed equally across all lines.

The education development index in Indonesia is still low. Based on data in the Education Index released by Human Development Reports, in 2017, Indonesia was in seventh place in ASEAN with a score of 0.622. The highest score was achieved by Singapore, that was 0.832, the second was Malaysia (0.719), the third was Brunei Darussalam (0.704), the fourth was Thailand and the Philippines that both had a score of 0.661, and the fifth was Vietnam with a score of 0.626 (Human Development Reports, 2017). Besides, the student ability survey in 2019 released by the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in Paris placed Indonesia in 72nd place out of 77 countries. Indonesia is in the bottom six rankings and it is still far below neighboring countries such as Malaysia and Brunei Darussalam. This PISA survey was conducted and became a reference in assessing the quality of education in the world by assessing reading, math and natural science skills (PISA reports, 2019). Improving the quality of education is important, especially to generate capable and competitive individuals in the world. This certainly does not only involve formal education, but also through non-formal education based on equality. The Ministry of Education and Culture made an equivalent education program in the 9 year compulsory education program, especially for children who dropped out of school through various levels such as package A equivalent to elementary school, package B equivalent to junior high school, and package C equivalent to SMA.

More specifically, educational equality is a non-formal education service guaranteed by law and intended for citizens who can't obtain formal education services for some reasons. One way to get this education is through homeschooling.

Homeschooling can be considered as part of the trend of increasing parental involvement in their children's education. The growing number of parents who choose homeschooling is encouraging researchers to conduct an investigation into this problem in the early 1980s (Leon, 2013). Most parents and children decide to implement homeschooling because of some reasons and change over the years (Resetar, 1990). The most prevalent reasons stated by parents or children for implementing homeschooling are to (a) adjust the child's educational needs, (b) obtain better academic achievement, (c) use the different pedagogical approach from those used in schools in general, (d) improve family relationships, (e) provide a safer learning environment, (f) avoid negative experiences suffered by parents once at school, and (g) fulfill the role of parents to teach and instill a set of values, beliefs, and perspectives of the world to their children who are not found in formal school (Murphy, 2012; Noel, Stark, & Redford, 2013; Stevens, 2001). Also, it can actually be considered as the final form of parental involvement in children's education (Neuman and Aviram, 2008). In many cases, homeschooling is considered beneficial for the development of a child's identity. The desire to protect children from the "negative effects" of formal education has been the appeal of homeschooling proponents. Homeschooling is part of attempts to achieve the functions and goals of national education that is to develop the skills and shape the character and a civilized nation with dignity to educate the life of the nation, aiming at developing the potential of learners to become human beings who believe in and fear God Almighty, virtuous, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens.

Homeschooling is also flexible. It can be conducted at home or at the educational institution that holds it. The forms of implementation of homeschooling learning also vary and certainly continue to make updates to improve the quality they have. From this background, the authors are interested in taking the main research problems: How is learning innovation in homeschooling in Indonesia? This is certainly to find out what innovations are in homeschooling for the development of better education in Indonesia, such as through equality education.

METHOD

In this research, the researchers chose Surakarta City as the research location. The authors focused on collecting data in the Surakarta area to see the existence and role of non-formal education in the form of homeschooling as an alternative education model in Surakarta. The primary data was taken from one of the homeschooling in Surakarta. This study used a qualitative method. Meanwhile, the research strategy used was case studies (Yin, R. K., 2011). The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling (Creswell, 2017). In this study, 14 informants were comprising of one key informant of the Director homeschooling, 4 informants of the homeschool staff per field, 3 teachers from various elementary and senior high school levels, 4 homeschool students with 1 student who was an alumnus, and 2 informants of the parents. Furthermore, data collection used participant observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation techniques. Data analysis used by the researchers was an interactive analysis model. Data analysis technique was an interactive analysis started with data reduction, followed by data presentation, and ended with drawing conclusions (Miles and Huberman, 2007). Finally, this study used source triangulation to test the credibility of the data, that was done by checking the data that had been obtained through several sources (Sugiyono, 2008).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the study, the researchers found some essential things related to the implementation of homeschooling as an alternative education model in Indonesia.. Homeschooling is not only an alternative education with rational practice but also an alternative education space (Kraftl, 2014). The background of its development is the issues related to education such as children with an abundance of work, children with special needs, parents who begin to doubt the quality of formal education, parents with high mobility that requires them to move across cities at any time.

Homeschooling Class System

Homeschooling has a different class system compared to formal schools in general. In Indonesia, primarily Homeschooling in Surakarta has 4 class systems, including individual class, community class, distance learning class, and non-mentoring/independent learning class system. Homeschooling has some students who are also commonly referred to as homeschoolers ranging from elementary, junior high, and senior high school levels. Their status is equivalent to formal school students generally.

Individual class is a class system for one student with learning activities performed following the schedule set by homeschooling. The learning atmosphere in the individual classes is almost the same as the community class, but it is done between one teacher and one student only. Interactions established during the learning process in the individual classroom system is more intense and can be more focused on the material being taught. Next is the community class.

This class is intended for 2 to 6 students with one teacher per subject in a study group done in homeschooling. Learning patterns are set and regulated by the school.. The next class system is an independent or non-accompaniment class. In this system, students are not required to come to school during learning activities. They can study independently or be accompanied (with parents/instructors outside homeschooling with the approval of the school/homeschool teachers) and students still obtain complete rights and facilities from the school. This class system only requires students to come to school in the Mid-Semester Assessment (PTS), Final Examinations (UAS), National-Based School Examination (USBN), National Examination (UNS), and external activities are done by the homeschool. The last, distance learning class. This is a special distance learning system for students who do not live in Surakarta City. This class is the establishment of an individual class. Learning media can utilize online video via Skype, Zoom, or other social media platforms between students and homeschool teachers. In the 2020/2021 school year, there were no students who took part in this class system because most of them lived in Surakarta.

Characteristics of Homeschool Students

The results of the study found that these students who choose to go to school based on interests and talents have various characteristics. The characteristics of these homeschool students are grouped by the authors as follows.

Table 1. Characteristics of Homeschool Students

Student Characteristics	Recommendations Given
Introverted student	Introverted students tend to have difficulty communicating with their friends. In this case, they are given the option to choose individual or community classes. The option of community class is given to get the appropriate classmates.
<i>Problematic Student</i>	Usually, students who had or are having personal problems are advised to take individual or independent classes and then are given regular assistance by staff of psychologists from the school.
Hyperactive student	Specifically, hyperactive students are advised to choose the individual or independent classes. This is to make the supervision is more controlled between teachers and students.
ABK (Children with Special Needs)	If possible, students with special needs can participate in school learning with an individual class system. However, if it does not apply, the choice to take part in independent learning is given.
<i>Normal Student</i>	This category consists of students who choose homeschooling with various considerations both from themselves and their parents. Some are due to bustle, some are due to the high mobility of their parents, some want to go to school but are reluctant to go to formal school, students who studied abroad, and students who want to experience a different learning atmosphere than usual.

The above data shows that the school provides optional recommendations to students who register and studies in homeschooling. The recommendations given are tailored to the needs of the students so that later learning activities and social interactions can be well established between teachers and students and among students. The category of introverted, hyperactive, and problematic students is given special assistance from homeschooling so that if a certain problem occurs, it can be directly consulted to the school to find a solution. It is also to continue to maintain the quality of learning in homeschooling. Whereas for students with special needs (ABK), student guardians are given the flexibility to consult with schools. This consultation aims to determine a child’s learning development.

Learning Hours at Homeschooling

The learning hours set in homeschooling are different from the one applied in formal schools. Homeschooling in Surakarta applies regular learning from Monday-Friday starts from 08.00 to 16.00 WIB. One lesson consists of 60 minutes. Students do not fully learn for 8 hours, but it is only limited based on their abilities and needs each day and they are only required to come for 3 times during the working day (Monday-Friday). Break time at homeschooling is 12.00 - 13.00 WIB. Subsequently, learning will be carried out according to an arranged schedule both for individual and community classes. For non-mentoring students/independent classroom system, learning hours are adjusted to the needs and abilities of these students accompanied by parents/student guardians or the teachers. The progress of student learning can be monitored through daily journals and reports from parents/teachers.

Objectives of Homeschooling Education

Homeschooling as one of the alternative non-formal educational institutions Surakarta City has several objectives, including to ensure the completion of primary and secondary education both for academic and non-academic learning

processes, to serve students who need flexible education to improve their potential, and to educate the nation's children to improve the quality of their lives. Homeschooling in Surakarta is interests and talents-based non-formal school so that the reference to student development is not only seen from their academic achievements but also the individual potential they have. The potential can be honed from childhood so that in homeschooling, this is an indicator to see how much the interests and talents of students. it means not only struggling in one field but can be from various fields in line with what is owned by the homeschool students.

Education Curriculum in Homeschooling

The curriculum implemented at Homeschooling in Surakarta has the same output and is equivalent to formal education in general. The curriculum is divided into 3 categories including curriculum that refers to the National standard (KURTILAS) or 2013 Curriculum which is adjusted to focus on the development of interests and talents and needs of students. Next, the International Curriculum (Cambridge International Examination or CIE) which is also modified by considering the development of interests and talents. The curriculum is divided into 3 levels: The International General Certificate of Secondary Education (IGCSE) for children aged 5-11 years, The General Certificate of Education Ordinary Level (GCE O Level) for children aged 14-16 years, and The General Certificate of Education Advanced Level Subsidiary and Advanced Level (GCE AS / A Level) for children aged 16-19 years. The last, there is an inclusive curriculum, which specifically serves children with special needs and is adapted from the National curriculum. Modifications are also tailored to the needs of students.

Educational Model in Homeschooling

Many educational models used in homeschooling include the "school at home" method which is the same educational model as the one held in schools generally; united studies which are theme-based education models; Charlotte Mason or the living book approach, which is the educational model through real experience; classical as an educational model that uses a structured curriculum based on three stages of child development; Waldorf as an educational model that seeks to create a school setting similar to the state of the house; Montessori as an educational model that prepares a natural environment to encourage children to interact with the environment; and Electics, as an educational model that provides an opportunity for families to design their homeschooling programs based on how to select or combine existing systems. Based on the results of research conducted by the authors, Homeschooling in Surakarta applies to learn with a "school at home" model, which indicates that it is almost the same as education performed in formal schools in general.

The curriculum used as described in the previous sub-chapter is the same as formal schools in general with adjustments based on the needs and abilities of students. The differences are the implementation of the learning process that is performed at home (schools in the form of a home), both individually and as a community in a friendly and family atmosphere. Besides, the material provided has an achievement standard with the same quality as the formal school curriculum. In assisting the learning process performed, Homeschooling uses two approaches including an approach with psychological aspects and an academic potential approach. This psychological approach is supported by the homeschool psychology division by first analyzing the students' background, aspects of interests, talents, and skills through various tests given. This test can be a majors test (for high school students), an intellectual intelligence test (IQ), and a talent interest test through fingerprints (DMI). The homeschool psychology division will first trace the background of the students starting from the previous school, the personality, and ask light questions to the students. It aims to build a close social relationship between psychology staff and students so that in the future when students experience a problem it can be consulted without hesitation. The majors test is carried out for high school students. The tests given are in the form of questions that must be done by students who register at Homeschooling. The results obtained are used to determine the majors of Natural Sciences or Social Sciences. Subsequently, there is a widely used IQ test. This test is performed not only in homeschooling but also in various places. The IQ test is used in homeschooling to detect whether there is mental retardation in students and intelligence and future career success.

At last, an interest and talent test using the DMI (fingerprint) method is conducted by homeschooling. Analysis test using this method can be used to analyze the talent, intelligence, learning style, and the character of students just by scanning the fingerprints of each student. The pattern of human fingerprints that are definite and permanent are useful to map brain function and reveal the student's personality. The use of the DMI test is expected to maximize the potential of each homeschool student. Once the results come out, students and parents will be given a report and explained in detail to help the child's future development.

Moreover, homeschooling also uses the academic potential approach. This approach focuses on learning systems that adjust and prioritize student learning modalities based on their level of skills, learning style, and character of communication. This approach is expected to see the extent the level of students' skills to receive material provided by the teacher either in the form of practice questions, daily tests, or others. The teacher also tries to modify the learning styles of students in homeschooling. Therefore, it is the essence of collaboration between the psychology division and the teachers because by knowing the results of the tests conducted and through the students' backgrounds, the learning styles can be adjusted as well. Learning styles applied are visual, auditory, and kinesthetic.

Table 2. Learning Styles of Homeschool Students

Type of Learning Style	Description
Visual Learning Style	This learning style is applied to students who have a tendency and interest in images. Therefore, visual understanding is better compared to others.
Auditory Learning Style	Auditory learning style focuses on student's hearing. It means that students who prefer the type of auditory learning style will rely more on their listening ability than taking notes.
Kinesthetic Learning Style	Kinesthetic learning style emphasizes the use of tools or media to receive information. This style is suitable for homeschool students who prefer direct practice and don't like to sit for long periods. In addition, students who do not speak loudly (slowly) can also accept this learning style.

In addition to the learning styles used, homeschooling also applies character education which is manifested in subjects and self-development activities in the form of extracurricular activities. All homeschool students are the primary target in the character education conducted. In learning, aspects of character education have included 18 character values following with the National Action Plan for Character Education (2010), including values of religion, independence, honesty, discipline, tolerance, hard work, creative, democratic, curiosity, national spirit, love the motherland, achievement appreciation, friendly/communicative character, love peace, love to read, care for the environment, care for the society, and responsibility. The "school at home" model, homeschooling learning style, and integrated values above are implemented in the learning process at Homeschooling in Surakarta to support student achievement and are expected to be able to instill good character and can be brought until later after graduating from homeschooling.

Education Socialization Performed in Homeschooling

Socialization is the process of instilling or transferring habits/values/rules including social interaction and social behavior. It is determined by the social, economic, and cultural environment in which the individual is settled. Besides, socialization can also come from real experiences encountered by students at school. In this case, the thing done is education socialization. The objective of education socialization is that homeschool students will be able to become good members of the society in terms of education, adjust their behavior according to the expectations of the community, know themselves, and realize their existence towards the community when it has plunged in their respective social environments. Homeschooling in Surakarta implements secondary socialization which is a type of continued socialization of primary socialization (which is received by an individual/child since childhood of 1-5-year-old before going to school). During the secondary socialization process, social relations that occur in education take place in an educational institution that is the school. Individuals or children are educated in accepting new norms and values. According to the results of the study, the secondary socialization process can be seen through the three stages that take place at school as follows:

Table 3. Process of Education Socialization in Homeschooling

Ongoing Socialization Process	Application in Homeschooling
The Process of Instilling Education Values and Norms (Internalization) through daily activities at school	This process is performed in homeschooling through daily academic and non-academic learning activities. For instance, students are encouraged to always arrive on time. This is not academic learning but an investment of values, which is the value of discipline and obeying the norms prevailing in schools. Regarding the academic, for example, through the subject of Sociology, students are taught related to various kinds of social deviations. The teacher not only teaches various forms of social deviation but also transfers knowledge that doing so is not good and is not accepted by the wider community.
Enculturation process	Enculturation is a social process performed by the individuals to learn and adjust their thoughts and attitudes to the customs, norm systems, social order, and rules in society. In this case, this process can occur starting with learning activities that mimic a number of actions. When at home, students imitate the family because the family is the place to do primary socialization. However, at school, the teacher will be the actor. The teacher exemplifies how the culture should be in the community so students can learn it. A small example is the inculcation of each student to respect the teacher, help each other in need, and get used to raising their hands before asking.

The process of self-maturity	Self-maturity is a process of ongoing internalization and enculturation. Primagama Homeschooling Solo has performed the process of internalization and enculturation so that it is not only instilling but there are also actions taken by students with the habituation they have done in their daily lives when at school. Carrying out these two processes will shape the personality of students which is expected to be even better.
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Secondary socialization performed by the school is considered essential because during education in homeschooling it is not impossible to obtain a lot of academic and non-academic learning. The three processes described above are performed so that students can understand themselves and be able to mingle into the community. The homeschool students at home and not doing daily activities at school also get similar socialization, that can be from teachers or parents. In this case, parents are also expected to be able to harmonize the values and rules imposed at school and can teach their children about learning culture (customs, values, and norms in society) so that they can be accepted in society later.

Supporting and Inhibiting Factors

Homeschooling is indeed an alternative model of education besides formal schooling which has many main benefits in children’s education. In its implementation, homeschooling also has factors that can support and inhibit the learning process. The results of the study show the supporting and inhibiting factors of alternative homeschooling education models as follows.

Table 4. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors to the Implementation of Homeschooling

Supporting Factors	Inhibiting Factors
Learning environment and facilities	The tuition fees tend to be expensive
Support from the school and family	Character adjustments of students, especially for ABK (Children with Special Needs)
The flexibility of the educational Curriculum	Supervision for the Homeschool Student
	The capabilities of parents when guiding children’s learning at home (for independent programs)

The table above shows that several factors are supporting the implementation of homeschooling education model. First is the learning environment and facilities. The limited homeschooling environment eases the monitoring process of the students. Besides, the small number of students compared to formal schools, in general, makes the teachers memorize more of their students so that when doing the learning and teaching process, they can know the progress of each student. Quite adequate homeschooling facilities for students also support learning activities at school and home. Second is the support from the school and family. It is essential, especially for homeschool students. Some students are introverted or have problems that can hamper the learning process. Therefore, support from teachers and parents in the form of motivation, enthusiasm, and other forms can make students have the confidence to do learning well. The third is the flexibility of the educational curriculum in homeschooling. In the previous sub-chapter, it has been explained regarding the three curriculums implemented in homeschooling. With the availability of the three, parents and students can be autonomous to determine the type of education will be taken and then it can be adjusted to the needs and abilities of students while still referring to applicable curriculum standards.

In addition to supporting factors, there are several inhibiting factors in the implementation of homeschooling. First is the cost of education which tends to be expensive. Homeschooling provides alternative education in addition to formal schooling which means that its status as a non-formal school makes it dependent on the cost of education in self-help for its process. Not all students in homeschooling are from the middle class. Some have sufficient economies or can be lacking but because they cannot attend formal school for some reasons, therefore, the parents choose homeschooling for their children’s education. The cost factor sometimes makes parents rethink to take this educational model. Second, is the character adjustment of homeschool students. There is a need for more collaboration between parents and teachers because of differences in character that need to be categorized. When doing the learning process in school and meeting students with unique characters, then the learning process becomes inhibited. It applies not only to community programs but also to individuals. Teachers must better understand the characteristics of students they teach so that in the future they can determine the steps they will take. For children with special needs (ABK), the treatment is also different. It needs more patience and efforts to develop good interactions. The next inhibiting factor is supervision for homeschool students. It needs optimal planning and supervision to determine the discipline and consistency of learning of students both at school and at home.

Finally, useful parental capabilities specifically for students who are doing independent/non-mentoring learning. The focus here is that parents need to understand the material that must be given and taught to their children both academically and non-academically. On one side, when schools hold activities that require all students from various programs to come to school, parents must also play an active role in asking their children to go to school. Since it is not uncommon for

homeschool students who study at home to be reluctant or difficult to come to school. The role of parents is also essential in the learning process here. Therefore, homeschooling also provides appeals and input, particularly for students who are doing independent learning. Parents are also advised to upgrade a variety of the latest information both for the academic learning process and related to other matters for the smooth running and development of students. The implementation of homeschooling, in general, has been going well, but still needs further improvements so that in the future it can meet the expectations of the society as an alternative education model other than non-formal schools.

Based on the findings in the field, the authors examine homeschooling as an alternative education model using social practice theory proposed by Pierre Bourdieu. Practice theory is the idea of Bourdieu's thought as a product of the relationship of habitus as a product of history and field which is also a product of history, where in the field there are battles, forces and people who have a great amount of capital, and people who do not have capital. Bourdieu stated this theory of social practice with the equation: $(\text{Habitus} \times \text{Capital}) + \text{Field} = \text{Practice}$. In a simple sense, habitus can be referred to as habits. It refers to dispositions created and formulated through a combination of objective structures and personal history (Huang, 2019). Habitus can be understood as a set of dispositions, which influence an individual's expectations of social life. The concept of habitus by Bourdieu is also related to the source of knowledge (Bourdieu 1990).

Based on the results of the study, habitus of Homeschooling in Surakarta is shown from the way of the learning patterns of students carried out. It starts from the registration of students who are usually open throughout the year except when they are going to take the midterm or final semester exams. Next, homeschooling also always provides recommendations for students who will join a homeschooling to take the most suitable classes for them (community, individual, or independent) so that in the future the learning process can take place well. For the curriculum to be taken, students are autonomous to choose the available curriculum except for the inclusive education curriculum which is specifically for ABK (Children with Special Needs) students. Students are also accustomed to always consult regularly with a psychologist at the homeschooling whether there is a problem or not. Besides, there is also a home visit which is one of the routines performed and to determine the extent of student development. Therefore, it is not just limited to school. Home visits are conducted on all students who study at homeschooling regularly so that personal problems can also be consulted right away. All of these things are performed to achieve a learning process with outputs that are in line with what is expected.

Besides habitus, another important thing mentioned by Bourdieu in practice theory is capital. Capital plays an essential role and is an asset owned to determine the position in a field. Capital must always be produced and reproduced. In Bourdieu's perspective, there are four types of capital, including economic capital, social capital, cultural capital, and symbolic capital (O'hara, 2000).

Economic Capital, which includes the means of production (machinery, land, labor), materials (earnings and objects) and money that are easily utilized for all purposes and passed down from one generation to the next (Bourdieu, 1993). Based on the results of research that has been done, Homeschooling has economic capital used to carry out its learning process continuously. The economic capital in the form of facilities used to support learning such as Wifi, AC (Air Conditioner), chairs, study desks, computers/PCs, mini-libraries, props, and classrooms. The availability of sufficient facilities is highly supportive, especially for teachers and students. Besides these facilities, there are also self-help funds that are used to renew or fix all the needs for improving the quality of Homeschooling in Surakarta. Funds that go to homeschooling come from tuition fees and semester fees that are paid as well as the monthly fees.

Cultural Capital, which includes all intellectual qualifications that can be produced through education or family inheritance, are obtained through individual initial learning and are unconsciously influenced by the environment (Bourdieu, 2000). For instance, the ability to present in public, ownership of high-value cultural objects, certain knowledge and expertise from the outcome of education, as well as certificates (degrees). In this case, Homeschooling as a non-formal educational institution has cultural capital. It can be seen from the teachers who teach at homeschooling who have their qualifications, indicating that they can adapt to students with different characters. Adaptation is done by adjusting learning patterns that are suitable for students, understanding the character of students, and providing support and motivation to them. Besides, students at Homeschooling also have cultural capital. Homeschooling is an interest and talent-based school that automatically students can hone their abilities and talents here through various extracurricular activities to support them. Achievements can be in the academic and non-academic aspects. Students who graduate from homeschooling also have a diploma resulting from the learning process, which is equivalent to formal schooling in general so that it can be used for their respective interests.

Social Capital, refers to social networks owned by actors (individuals or groups) related to other parties who have power (Bourdieu, 1993). Homeschooling in Surakarta has a partnership with homeschooling Network throughout Indonesia, both from the central and branch homeschooling. It is not only homeschooling but also has connections with all branches. Besides, cooperation with local governments is also being implemented related to the problems of legality and homeschool licensing, in this case, the Surakarta City Education and Culture Office. With good synergy, the run of homeschooling as an alternative education model in Surakarta in the future can be better known by the whole community

so that it can provide learning options at school in addition to formal education. This social network can also improve the confidence of the wider community to send their children to homeschooling.

Symbolic Capital, includes all forms of prestige, status, authority and legitimacy. In this sense, the status of Homeschooling as a non-formal educational institution in Surakarta City based on interests and talents becomes essential. Homeschooling becomes a non-formal school known by the wider community as alternative education for children who need it. Furthermore, children can develop their interests and talents while getting academic learning. Therefore, they can have non-academic achievements that can be honed through extracurricular activities and other support available in homeschooling.

Table 6. Matrix of Capitals Owned by Homeschooling

No	Type of Capital	Primagama Homeschooling Solo
1.	Economic Capital	Sufficient facilities such as AC, Wifi, classrooms, consultation rooms, chairs, study desks, computers/PCs, mini-libraries, and props. Besides the facilities, self-funding is also one of the essential capitals in homeschooling.
2.	Cultural Capital	The teachers' skills to talk and adapt to their students so they can do social interaction well. Besides, students also have cultural capital, which is the expertise gained after learning both academically and non-academically at Primagama, which is improving the quality and individual skills. Students who go to homeschooling also get a diploma equivalent to a typical school.
3.	Social Capital	Wide network. It can be exemplified by Primagama Solo that has a network of all Primagama homeschooling both central and branch as well as Primagama (tutoring) in Indonesia, Surakarta City Education and Culture Office, and several umbrella schools.
4.	Symbolic Capital	The status of Primagama Homeschooling Solo as a non-formal educational institution provides alternative education based on interests and talents. Therefore, in addition to being an alternative for students who need education other than formal schooling, they can establish their interests and talents and provide support to achieve what they want.

Based on the results of the study, from the four capitals, the authors draw the conclusion that there is two essential and prominent capital. Although the four capitals are essential, there is capital that must be owned for the future of Homeschooling in the future, which is the economic capital and social capital. Economic capital is an essential capital. It is because homeschooling is a non-formal (private) school, which means it requires self-funding from the community who entrusts to send their children to homeschooling. The inadequacy of sufficient funds will inhibit the future process of the homeschooling. Besides, facilities are also needed to support student learning in homeschooling. Without adequate facilities, the resulting learning process will be less than optimal. Moreover, social capital becomes essential because the network formed between Homeschooling in Surakarta with other institutions/foundations can provide benefits and can make homeschooling more developed. By establishing synergy with government institutions, umbrella schools, and all homeschooling branches in Indonesia can support learning activities by exchanging ideas related to policy, learning processes, upgrading, implementation of the National Examination, and others.

It has been discussed above regarding habitus and capital owned by Homeschooling in Surakarta. Subsequently, there is an arena or field. The field can be interpreted as a type of competitive open market, where many kinds of capital (economic, cultural, social, symbolic) are utilized and distributed. Capital can be obtained if one has the right habitus. By having the right habitus and capital, the opportunity to succeed in the field will be even greater. The field intended in this case is the field of education. In the education field, Homeschooling with proper habitus and capital can carry out the learning process and non-formal schooling based on interests and talents in Surakarta City well.

Habitus, capital, and field are inseparable units. All three must be mutually sustainable to produce an appropriate social practice for the achievement of the goals of homeschooling and the creation of alternative models of educational homeschooling based on interests and talents known in the community so that they can meet the needs of their students. Homeschooling is one of the schools that provide alternative education based on interests and talents in Surakarta City. Habitus and existing capital support the learning process in homeschooling going well. Furthermore, it can be concluded that homeschooling education has not been completely liberating. Critical awareness has not yet formed on all aspects of both the homeschooling side as well as parents and students.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research and discussion that has been described, it can be concluded that education is important learning of knowledge and skills, especially for the future of a child. Seeing the many problems of children ranging from the number of children with an abundance of work, children with special needs, parents who begin to doubt the quality of formal education, parents with high mobility that requires them to move across cities at any time, and various personal problems experienced by children, therefore homeschooling is available as one of the alternative education models in Surakarta City. As an alternative education model, this institution has differences with formal schools in general. First, 4 class systems are owned including community classes with 2-6 students, individual classes with one teacher and student, independent/non-mentoring classes that take place at home can be accompanied by parents, homeschool teachers or outside homeschooling, and distance learning class for students from outside Surakarta City. Second, homeschool students have different characters which the authors divided into 5 categories, including introverted students, problematic students, hyperactivity, ABK, and normal students. Third, learning in homeschooling lasts for 2-3 per day and 3 times a week with students taking individual/community classes at school. Meanwhile, students who study at home also adjust schedules according to the rules of homeschooling. Fourth, there are 3 applicable curricula, including the 2013 curriculum, Cambridge International Examination, and inclusive education modified according to student needs. From all aspects, the ongoing learning process can be considered to be quite good and meet the needs of students in homeschooling.

Application of the "school at home" model, which indicates that it is almost similar to schools in general. Although there are differences as explained before, the outputs and rules that implement are in line with existing standards and follow the test with the equality package. In its implementation, Homeschooling in Surakarta also applies character education based on 18 values in accordance with the National Action Plan for Character Education. The relationship between teacher and student in homeschooling is different from that of formal schools in general. The teacher must also understand the students well based on their respective characters so that learning can run smoothly and well. Because it is an interest and talent-based school, there are other supporting activities such as field trips, outbound, and extracurricular activities. Education socialization that took place at homeschooling can be concluded to have run well through 3 stages, including the process of instilling values and educational norms (internalization) through daily activities at school, the process of enculturation, and the process of self-maturity. The expectation is that students can become better individuals and get involved in the community later.

Homeschooling in Surakarta as an alternative education model is also reviewed by the authors using two theories of the theory of social practices by Bourdieu. First, using Bourdieu's theory, it is seen from the habitus owned by homeschooling as shown by how the pattern of student learning conducted starting from student registration which is usually always open throughout the year except when it approaches the midterm or final semester exams. Next, homeschooling also always provides recommendations for students who will join a homeschooling to take the most suitable classes for them (community, individual, or independent) so that in the future the learning process can run well. Students are also accustomed to always consult routinely with a psychologist at the homeschooling whether there is a problem or not. In addition, there is also a home visit which is one of the regular activities performed and to determine the extent of student development. Therefore, it is not only limited to school. The four capital also plays an important role in this matter, including economic, cultural, social, and symbolic capital. However, according to the authors, of the four capital, there is two capital that must exist for the continuity of homeschooling, including economic capital and social capital. In the education field, homeschooling with proper habitus and capital can perform the learning process and non-formal schooling based on interests and talents in Surakarta City well.

Suggestions given by the authors include: (1) non-formal educational institutions, especially Homeschooling in Surakarta should be able to improve quality and service. It can be done by adding learning facilities, socializing education and interacting more frequently with students to build a comfortable learning atmosphere, and evaluating the curriculum in stages. To overcome the cost problem, the school can provide relief in the form of payment in stages. Therefore, students who attend the school can continue the learning process. Subsequently, to adjust the character of students and supervision, new personnel/teachers can be added in their fields or teacher training to handle students with special needs/ABK, (2) the government is expected to be able to provide support or introduce the concept of alternative education models in the form of homeschooling such as in Surakarta City. Besides homeschooling in Surakarta, other homeschooling also can be made possible so that it can be a solution for some people who need education or for children who do not want to go to formal school, (3) further researchers are expected to provide a wider study, especially related to homeschooling as an alternative model of this education supported from many sources and existing research references. The further researchers also prepare themselves in its main field when dealing with unexpected things such as informants who are difficult to interview, data that is difficult to obtain, and so forth.

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